

UTILIZATION OF GENRE-BASED FOR WRITING SKILLS OF PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS IN PHILIPPINE WOMEN'S UNIVERSITY CALAMBA

Jenelyn D. Abanis

English Department Laguna College of Business and Arts Calamba City, Laguna, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15673951>

ABSTRACT

This study examined the effectiveness of the Genre-Based approach (GBA) in enhancing the writing skills of pre-service teachers at Philippine Women's University Calamba. Utilizing a quasi-experimental design, it assessed whether GBA can significantly improve students' writing performance in cognitive awareness, linguistic awareness, rhetorical awareness, and genre awareness. The study involved an experimental group using GBA and a control group following traditional writing instruction. Both groups underwent pretest and posttest assessing their literature analysis skills across four areas using a 40-item multiple choice test. Results revealed significant improvements in both groups with the experimental group displaying greater progress. Mean differences in the experimental group were: cognitive awareness (-2.08, $p=.000$), linguistic awareness (16.25, $p=.004$), rhetorical awareness (-26.67, $p=.000$), and genre awareness (-13.33, $p=.009$). The control group also gains: cognitive awareness (-10.42, $p=.001$), linguistic awareness (-15.83, $p=.000$), rhetorical awareness (-10.00, $p=.013$), and genre awareness (-13.33, $p=.003$). Findings indicate that integrating GBA into writing instruction enhances student performance, particularly for those needing additional support. GBA serves as a valuable supplement to traditional approaches, fostering foundational writing skills. Further research is recommended to explore its long-term effects and integration with other instructional approaches. Overall, GBA proves to be an effective strategy for strengthening students' written communication, making it a viable option for educators in teacher training programs.

Keywords: *utilization, genre-based approach, writing skills, pre-service teachers, PWU*

INTRODUCTION

Writing was widely seen as the most demanding skill to master in language learning because it required deep cognitive involvement, precise language use, and complex rhetorical abilities (Hidayad et al., 2023). Unlike speaking, which allowed for immediate clarification and feedback, writing involved careful planning, organization, and revision to clearly express ideas. The researcher observed that many pre-service teachers struggled to form coherent sentences and meaningful compositions. Factors that contributed to these challenges included limited exposure to different writing genres, fear of failure, and writing-related anxiety. The task became more complicated as learners had to manage grammar, vocabulary, and coherence while also considering the audience, purpose, and conventions of each genre. As pointed out by Zhai and Razali (2023) writing proficiency remained a significant concern in education worldwide, with students often failing to meet expected academic and professional standards. Additionally, writing difficulties were not only linguistic but also cultural and contextual. Effective writing required not just grammatical correctness but also an understanding of culturally appropriate ways to structure arguments and present evidence (Kinik & Genc, 2022). Addressing these difficulties called for comprehensive support, including explicit instruction in writing strategies, ample practice opportunities, and culturally responsive teaching

Local research, such as studies by Garcia and Reyes (2021) and Santos et al. (2023) explored writing instruction strategies but did not specifically examine the use of the Genre-Based Approach. This gap was particularly concerning in the Philippines, where increasing classroom diversity meant students from various linguistic, cultural, and socioeconomic backgrounds faced unique challenges in academic and professional writing. Writing proficiency in the Philippines reflected a broader global issue. In 2020, the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) reported that only 63% of Filipino students met the minimum writing proficiency for their grade level, with nearly half at the lowest proficiency levels, highlighting the urgent need for targeted interventions. Writing challenges in the Philippines, such as limited exposure to different genres and language barriers, were intensified by global trends, as even developed countries struggled to improve students' writing skills. Urbano et al. (2021) further noted that in Metro Manila, senior high school students faced numerous academic writing challenges, including insufficient topic knowledge, unfamiliarity with citation practices, grammatical errors, limited vocabulary, and improper use of development patterns.

Given the scarcity of local studies examining this instructional method, there was a clear need for research that not only assesses its effectiveness in improving writing abilities but also adapted its strategies to the unique cultural and educational setting of the Philippines. Therefore, based on the findings of this study, it was advised to develop a comprehensive writing program rooted in the principles of the Genre-Based Approach.

Furthermore, the importance of integrating genre-based instruction into the Philippine education system became evident, considering the global emphasis on communicative competence and the need for students to produce contextually

appropriate texts. The Genre-Based Approach (GBA) emphasized teaching students to recognize and produce different types of texts according to the conventions specific to each genre, thus enabling learners to develop their writing skills systematically. Implementing GBA in Filipino classrooms could have helped students better understand the structural and linguistic features of various genres such as argumentative essays, reports, summaries, and research papers. It also encouraged learners to analyze authentic texts, which could improve their understanding of genre-specific language use and rhetoric strategies.

However, the successful implementation of GBA required trained teachers who understood the principles and practice of genre-based teaching. Professional development programs needed to be designed to equip educators with the necessary skills to guide students through the process of genre analysis, planning, drafting, and revising. Additionally, incorporating culturally responsive teaching strategies within the GBA framework could have addressed the diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds of Filipino students, making writing instruction more relevant and engaging.

In conclusion, addressing the complex challenges of writing in the Philippine context called for a multidimensional approach that combined effective instructional strategies like the Genre-Based Approach with teacher training, student-centered activities, and culturally sensitive practices. Such initiatives could have significantly contributed to improving students' writing proficiency, better preparing them for academic success and professional communication in a rapidly globalizing world.

Research Questions

This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of the Genre-Based Approach in improving the English writing proficiency of pre-service teachers enrolled in the Children and Adolescent Literature course at Philippine Women's University Calamba during the second semester of the 2024-2025 academic year.

It specifically answered the following questions:

1. What is the pretest score of the pre-service teachers in the control group in the English writing proficiency in terms of:
 - 1.1 Cognitive Awareness,
 - 1.2 Linguistic Awareness,
 - 1.3 Rhetorical Awareness, and
 - 1.4 Genre Awareness?
2. What is the pretest score of the pre-service teachers in the experimental group in the English writing proficiency in terms of:
 - 2.1 Cognitive Awareness,
 - 2.2 Linguistic Awareness,
 - 2.3 Rhetorical Awareness, and
 - 2.4 Genre Awareness?
3. Is there a significant difference between the pretest scores of the control and experimental group?

4. What is the posttest score of the pre-service teachers in the control group in the English writing proficiency in terms of:
 - 4.1 Cognitive Awareness,
 - 4.2 Linguistic Awareness,
 - 4.3 Rhetorical Awareness, and
 - 4.4 Genre Awareness?
5. What is the posttest score of the pre-service teachers in the experimental group in the English writing proficiency in terms of:
 - 5.1 Cognitive Awareness,
 - 5.2 Linguistic Awareness,
 - 5.3 Rhetorical Awareness, and
 - 5.4 Genre Awareness?
6. Is there a significant difference between the posttest scores of the control and experimental group?
7. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the control and experimental groups?
8. Based on the findings of the study, what writing program may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

The research was conducted at Philippine Women's University Calamba, Laguna, a private higher education institution that offered various academic programs, including the Bachelor of Secondary Education majoring in English (BSED). This program is known for developing proficiency in English grammar, writing, literature, linguistics, and communication skills, along with teaching methodologies tailored to secondary education. For this study, the focus was on the pre-service teachers enrolled in Children and Adolescent Literature course during the second semester of the 2024-2025 academic year.

Population and Sampling

The population of this study consisted of second-year pre-service teachers enrolled at the Philippine Women's University of Calamba during the second semester of the 2024-2025 academic year, specifically those taking the Children and Adolescent Literature course. The study focused on one preexisting section, which was divided into control and experimental group. Twelve female pre-service teachers were assigned to the control group, while the another twelve female pre-service teachers were assigned to the experimental group. Although both groups followed the same curriculum, the implementation of the GBA differentiated the instructional approach distinguished the instructional methods used between the two groups.

To ensure academic comparability, the study used purposive sampling to select participants who met specific criteria relevant to the research. Additionally, both the control and experimental groups were equally represented. The writing skills of participants were assessed using both a pretest and posttest.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were selected from the second-year pre-service teachers enrolled in the Philippine Women’s University of Calamba during the second semester of the 2024-2025 academic year, specifically those taking the Children and Adolescent Literature course. The study focused on two groups: the control group, which was taught using traditional teaching methods, and the experimental group, which was taught by the researcher using the Genre-based approach.

A total of 12 pre-service teachers were chosen from each group, making a combined total of 24 participants. The selection was based on their pretest score to ensure that students from both the control and experimental groups were academically comparable at baseline. This approach helped in accurately determining the effect of Genre-based approach on pre-service teachers’ writing skills.

Considering the participants’ gender and their pretest performance as a baseline in their English writing skills, the study strengthened its capacity to generalize findings and draw significant conclusions about the effectiveness of utilizing the Genre-based approach with pre-service teachers. Furthermore, controlling for these variables supports the applicability of the findings to broader populations of pre-service teachers, offering valuable insights for educators aiming to implement genre-based in writing instruction.

Table A *Distribution of Respondents*

Group	Year Level	Gender	No. of respondents	Percentage
Control	2-BSED	F-12	12	50%
Experimental	2-BSED	F-12	12	50%
Total		F-24	24	100%

Table A showed the distribution of participants in the study. The participants were divided equally into two groups: the control and the experimental group, each consisting of 12 pre-service teachers from second-year level. Both groups were composed entirely of female respondents, totaling 24 participants. Each group represented 50% of the total respondents, making the overall sample size of 24, which accounted for 100% of the participants involved in the study.

Instrument

This study employed pretests and post-tests to collect data needed to evaluate the respondents' English writing proficiency both prior to and following the implementation of the Genre-based Approach. The pretest and posttest, developed by the researcher, included four sections: 10 multiple-choice questions evaluating cognitive awareness, 10 items assessing linguistic awareness, 10 items measuring rhetorical awareness, and 10 items targeting genre awareness. The 5-point Likert Scale was used to assess the English writing proficiency of the pre-service teachers, a 90-100 Proficient, 85-89 Advanced, 80-84 Intermediate, 75-79 Basic, and 74 below as Beginner.

By breaking down writing proficiency into cognitive, linguistic, rhetorical, and genre awareness, the instrument aimed to capture a detailed profile of students' abilities and assess the effectiveness of the genre-based approach in enhancing the writing skills of pre-service teachers.

Likert Scale

90 - 100	Proficient (P)
85 - 89	Advanced (A)
80 - 84	Intermediate (I)
75 - 79	Basic (B)
74	below Beginner (B)

Validation of Instrument

To guarantee the reliability and precision of the assessment tool employed in this study, both the pretest and posttest underwent a validation process. The main instrument used to evaluate the pre-service teachers' writing skills was a research-made tool, specifically designed to measure their writing proficiency.

The selection of four key areas: cognitive awareness, linguistic awareness, rhetorical awareness, and genre awareness was derived from the theory of Cognitivism and Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development, which provided a comprehensive framework for understanding and improving students writing skills. The questions were carefully designed evaluate students' skills in these key areas, ensuring that the assessment was thorough and closely aligned with the study's emphasis on the Genre-based approach.

To ensure its validity, the instrument was evaluated, these included the thesis adviser, the Research Director, the Research Statistician, and two professionals specializing in English language teaching. These validators reviewed the test items to confirm that they effectively measured the intended writing skill components. Each item was assessed using a 3-point relevance scale, 1 as essential, 2 as Useful but not Essential, and 3 as Not Necessary. Their feedback was used to improve the clarity and relevance of the test items. The final version of the test was then administered for both the pretest and posttest.

The evaluation conducted by five validators indicated that, out of the 40 items on the test, only 2 questions received a score of 2, which signified that they were useful but not essential and therefore retained in the test. The remaining items each received a perfect score of 1, indicating that they were considered essential for the assessment. This scoring suggested that the majority of the items were relevant and crucial for measuring the intended learning outcomes. Moreover, the overall Content Validity Index (CVI) was calculated to be 0.92, which was considered very high and demonstrates strong agreement among the validators regarding the relevance and essentiality of the test items. This high CVI value confirmed that the test items were valid and appropriate for evaluating the students' writing skills within the context of the study.

The study utilized a quasi-experimental design, pilot testing was not performed since the research focused on evaluating the effect of the genre-based approach within an existing academic course. Instead, the validity of the instrument was confirmed through expert review and feedback process. Subject matter experts in English language teaching and writing pedagogy were consulted to assess the content relevance, clarity, and alignment of the instrument with the study's objectives without requiring preliminary testing.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before collecting data, the researcher prepared a letter requesting permission for data gathering, which was reviewed and approved by the research adviser. After this approval, the letter was taken to LCBA for the signature of the Graduate Studies dean, and then forwarded to Philippine Women's University for the Academic Dean's endorsement. Once all approvals were secured, the researcher administered the pretest to both the control and experimental groups to evaluate their writing skills, specifically measuring cognitive, linguistic, rhetorical, and genre awareness prior to the intervention. The pretest consisted of 40 multiple-choice questions. Following the pretest, the experimental group received instruction through the Genre-based Approach, integrating content from the Children and Adolescent Literature course with English as the medium of instruction. Meanwhile, the control group was taught using traditional methods aligned with the standard curriculum. Both groups covered the same course material, but only the experimental group utilized the Genre-based Approach. After the intervention, both groups completed a posttest similar to the pretest to assess any improvements in their writing skills across the same four areas.

The intervention took place from March 10 to April 7, 2025, spanning five class meetings. The 24 participants were divided into two classes based on the university's schedule, which mandates a congested weekly meeting for each class, with each subject taught for three hours per week. The researcher allocated one hour and forty-five minutes per session every Monday for both groups. Additionally, the experimental group had a one-hour output consultation every Wednesday for peer review and reflection, as part of the Genre-based Approach implementation stages. This schedule was approved by the university's Academic Dean and the experimental group participants.

Finally, the pretest and posttest results were analyzed using statistical methods, including paired t-tests, to determine the effectiveness of the Genre-based Approach on the students' writing skills.

Scope and Delimitation

This study concentrated on pre-service teachers enrolled in the Children and Adolescent Literature course at Philippine Women's University during the second semester of the 2024-2025 academic year. It examined the effectiveness of the Genre-Based Approach in enhancing students' writing abilities, focusing specifically on cognitive, linguistic, rhetorical, and genre awareness. Employing a quasi-experimental design over one semester term, the study involved an experimental group that received instruction through the Genre-Based Approach, while a control group was taught using traditional methods. The impact of the approach was assessed by comparing pretest and posttest scores of both groups across the targeted writing skill areas.

The limitations of this study should be recognized. First, the findings were specific to pre-service teachers enrolled in the Children and Adolescent Literature course at Philippine Women's University Calamba and may not be generalize to students from other schools or different educational contexts. Second, the study focused solely on writing skills within the scope of the Children and Adolescent Literature course, excluding other subjects or language skills such as reading and speaking.

Lastly, the genres examined in this study were limited to poetry, myths, epics, fiction, and folk tales, as outlined in the course syllabus. Additionally, the study was confined to the sample of students available during the 2024-2025 academic year, which may restrict the applicability of the results to a wider student population.

RESULTS

Research Question 1. What is the pretest score of the pre-service teachers in the control group in the English writing proficiency in terms of:

- 1.1 Cognitive Awareness,
- 1.2 Linguistic Awareness,
- 1.3 Rhetorical Awareness, and
- 1.4 Genre Awareness?

Table 1.1 Pretest Score of the Pre-service Teachers in the Control Group in English Writing Proficiency in terms of Cognitive Awareness

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	0	0
Advanced	3	25.0

Intermediate	1	8.3
Basic	5	41.7
Beginner	3	25.0
Total	12	100.00
Average	76.25	Basic
SD	6.44	

Legend : 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate 75 - 79 Basic 74 below Beginner

The pretest score of the pre-service teachers in the control group fell under **Basic** category with an average score of **76.25** in their English writing proficiency in terms of cognitive awareness and a standard deviation of 6.44. There were (41.7%) pre-service teachers who were in the Basic category, (25%) in the Beginner, (25%) Advanced, and (8.3%) fell under Intermediate. Notably, no pre-service teachers fell under Proficient level. It implies that the performance in the control group suggests that there is a need to strengthen their foundational skills in English writing proficiency particularly in cognitive awareness. These findings are connected with the study of Can (2021) who highlighted that incorporating literature into English instruction aided students in grasping the practical application of language, while the cultural values embedded in the literature encourage the growth of critical thinking skills.

Table 1.2 Pretest Score of Pre-service Teachers in the Control Group in English Writing Proficiency in terms of Linguistic Awareness

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	0	0
Advanced	0	0
Intermediate	0	0
Basic	0	0
Beginner	12	100
Total	12	100.00
Average	66.67	Beginner
SD	5.77	

Legend : 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate 75 - 79 Basic 74 below Beginner

The pretest score of the pre-service teachers in the control group fell in the **Beginner** category with an average score of **66.67** in their English writing proficiency in terms of linguistic awareness and a standard deviation of 5.77. There were (100%) pre-service teachers who were in the Beginner level, and no pre-service teachers fell under the proficient, Advanced, Intermediate, and Basic levels. It implies that the absence of any students in the higher performance categories such as proficient, advanced, and intermediate has significant implications for teaching and learning. This data suggests that there are significant gaps in the curriculum or teaching methods that need to be addressed. In line with this, Haryanti and colleagues (2022) found that language awareness had a significant direct effect on participants' writing performance.

Additionally, writing attitude influenced writing achievement indirectly, with language awareness serving as a mediating factor.

Table 1.3 Pretest Score of the Pre-service Teachers in the Control Group in English Writing Proficiency in terms of Rhetorical Awareness

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	0	0
Advanced	0	0
Intermediate	1	8.3
Basic	3	25.0
Beginner	8	66.7
Total	12	100.00
Average	70.00	Beginner
SD	6.03	

Legend : 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate 75 - 79 Basic 74 below Beginner

The pretest score of the pre-service teachers in the control group fell under **Beginner** category with an average score of **70.00** in their English writing proficiency in terms of rhetorical awareness and a standard deviation of 6.03. There were (66.7%) pre-service teachers who were in the Beginner level, (25%) Basic, and (8.3%) who were in the Intermediate category. Notably, there were no pre-service teachers fell under Proficient and Advanced level.

This implies that traditional training methods fail to cultivate higher-order writing strategies, such as persuasive structuring or genre-specific adaptation. Overall, these findings imply a need for targeted instructional interventions that explicitly foster rhetorical awareness, higher-order thinking skills to improve writing proficiency among pre-service teachers to better support their future students in mastering complex writing tasks, especially those at the beginner level.

Same conclusions were drawn by Jensen and Dean (2022) that rhetorical techniques were methods writers used to effectively organize their ideas, including structuring essays, arranging paragraphs, and developing arguments. Dean also highlighted the importance of coherence and cohesion in writing, where transitional phrases and clear topic sentences guide the reader smoothly through the text. By mastering these rhetorical techniques, writers can craft persuasive, well-organized, and meaningful essays that effectively communicate their intended messages.

Table 1.4 Pretest Score of the Pre-service Teachers in the Control Group in English Writing Proficiency in terms of Genre Awareness.

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	0	0
Advanced	0	0

Intermediate	0	0
Basic	3	25.0
Beginner	9	75.0
Total	12	100.00
Average	68.75	Beginner
SD	4.33	

Legend : 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate 75 - 79 Basic 74 below Beginner

The pretest score of the pre-service teachers in the control group fell under **Beginner** category with an average score of **68.75** in their English writing proficiency in terms of genre awareness and a standard deviation of 4.33. There were (75%) pre-service teachers who were in the Beginner category, (25%) who were in the Basic. These findings suggest that existing instructional methods or curricular content do not adequately address students' learning needs, either due to insufficient scaffolding, misaligned teaching strategies, or a lack of targeted practice opportunities.

Research Question 2. What is the pretest score of the pre-service teachers in the experimental group in the English writing proficiency in terms of:

- 2.1 Cognitive Awareness,
- 2.2 Linguistic Awareness,
- 2.3 Rhetorical Awareness, and
- 2.4 Genre Awareness?

Table 2.1 Pretest Score of the Pre-service Teachers in the Experimental Group in English Writing Proficiency in terms of Cognitive Awareness

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	0	0
Advanced	1	8.3
Intermediate	2	16.7
Basic	3	25.0
Beginner	6	75.0
Total	12	100.00
Average	72.08	Beginner
SD	7.53	

Legend : 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate 75 - 79 Basic 74 below Beginner

The pretest score of the pre-service teachers in the experimental group fell under **Beginner** category with an average score of **72.08** in their English writing proficiency in terms of cognitive awareness and a standard deviation of 7.53. There were (75%) pre-service teachers who were in the Beginner category, (25%) Basic, (16.7) Intermediate and (8.3%) Advanced. Notably, no pre-service teachers fell under Proficient level.

This implies that while some students are capable of higher-level performance, systemic instructional gaps may be failing to elevate the broader student base. The

majority's stagnation at beginner level points to potential deficiencies in foundational content delivery, or a lack of differentiated instruction tailored to diverse learning process.

Table 2.2 Pretest Score of the Pre-service Teachers in the Experimental Group in English Writing Proficiency in terms of Linguistic Awareness

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	0	0
Advanced	0	0
Intermediate	2	16.7
Basic	1	8.3
Beginner	9	75.3
Total	12	100.00
Average	66.67	Beginner
SD	8.62	

Legend : 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate 75 - 79 Basic 74 below Beginner

The pretest score of the pre-service teachers in the experimental group fell under **Beginner** category with an average score of **66.67** in their English writing proficiency in terms of linguistic awareness and a standard deviation of 8.62. There were (75.3%) pre-service teachers who were in the Beginner category, (16.7%) Intermediate, and (8.3%) fell under Basic category. Notably, no pre-service teachers fell under Proficient and Advanced level.

This implies that the dominance of beginner- level performance suggests that most pre-service teachers lack mastery in essential areas such as grammar, syntax, and structural clarity. Furthermore, this low proficiency suggests difficulties in organizing ideas coherently and applying appropriate writing conventions, which are critical for effective communication. The inadequate writing skills may affect their confidence and motivation to engage in writing tasks, potentially impacting their overall academic and professional development.

Table 2.3 Pretest Score of the Pre-service Teachers in the Experimental Group in English Writing Proficiency in terms of Rhetorical Awareness

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	0	0
Advanced	0	0
Intermediate	0	0
Basic	3	25.0
Beginner	9	75.0
Total	12	100.00
Average	65.00	Beginner
SD	7.69	

Legend : 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate 75 - 79 Basic 74 below Beginner

The pretest score of the pre-service teachers in the experimental group fell under **Beginner** category with an average score **65.00** in their English writing proficiency in terms of rhetorical awareness and a standard deviation of 7.69. There were (75%) pre-service teachers who were in the Beginner, and (25%) fell under Basic. Notably, no pre-service teachers fell under Proficient, Advanced, and Intermediate level.

It implies that many students struggle to understand the expectations of academic writing and lack of sufficient knowledge of rhetorical awareness. As a result, they may find difficult to effectively tailor their writing to different audiences, purposes, and contexts, which are essential skills for clear and persuasive communication. Findings by Dunn (2022) stressed that mastering rhetorical techniques improves an author’s capacity to persuade and convince readers effectively. This involves choosing appropriate argumentative elements, organizing the structure, and developing the style to create a well-crafted text.

Table 2.4 Pretest Score of the Pre-service Teachers in the Experimental Group in English Writing Proficiency in terms of Genre Awareness

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	2	16.7
Advanced	1	8.3
Intermediate	3	25.0
Basic	1	8.3
Beginner	5	41.7
Total	12	100.00
Average	77.92	Beginner
SD	12.52	

Legend : 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate 75 - 79 Basic 74 below Beginner

The pretest score of the pre-service teachers in the control group fell under **Beginner** category with an average score of **77.92** in their English writing proficiency in terms of genre awareness and a standard deviation of 12.52. There were (41.7%) pre-service teachers fell under Beginner category, (25%) Intermediate, (16.7) Proficient, 8.3% Advanced, and 8.3% fell under Basic level.

The implication of these findings suggests that the current teaching methods or resources are inconsistently effective, potentially due to varying learner engagement, differentiated support gaps, or uneven access to skill-building opportunities. In the study of Tardy et al. (2023) it was observed that the genre approach served as a flexible and dynamic framework, equipping English Language Learners (ELLs) with the necessary tools to adapt their writing effectively to various contexts, audiences, and purposes in order to meet their communication objectives.

Research Question 3. Is there a significant difference between the pretest scores of the control and experimental groups?

Table 3 Test of Significant Difference Between the Pretest Scores of the Control and Experimental Groups

Variables	T test	P value	Remarks	Decision
Pretest	.056	.956	Not Significant	Accept Ho

There was **no significant difference** in the pretest score of the control and experimental groups in terms of cognitive awareness, linguistic awareness, rhetorical awareness, and genre awareness. The T-test value was .056 and probability value was .956 which was greater than the level of significance at .05. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted.

These findings underscore the importance of the pretest phase in establishing a reliable starting point, as it confirms that any post-intervention differences observed between the groups can be more confidently attributed to the experimental treatment rather than pre-existing disparities. As indicated by Gopalan and Tipton (2023) that having similar pretest scores between groups improved both the internal validity and the generalizability of the effects of an intervention.

Research Question 4. What is the posttest score of the pre-service teachers in the control group in the English writing proficiency in terms of:

- 4.1 Cognitive Awareness,**
- 4.2 Linguistic Awareness,**
- 4.3 Rhetorical Awareness, and**
- 4.4 Genre Awareness?**

Table 4.1 Posttest Score of the Pre-service Teachers in the Control Group in English Writing Proficiency in terms of Cognitive Awareness

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	5	41.6
Advanced	2	16.7
Intermediate	3	25.0
Basic	2	16.7
Beginner	0	0
Total	12	100.00
Average	86.67	Advanced

Legend : 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate 75 - 79 Basic 74 below Beginner

The posttest score of the pre-service teachers in the control group fell under **Advanced** category with an average score of **86.67** in their English writing proficiency in terms of cognitive awareness and a standard deviation of 9.13. There were (41.6%) pre-service teachers who were in the Proficient category, (25%) Intermediate, (16.7%) Advanced, (16.7%) Basic, and no pre-service teacher fell under Beginner level. This implies that instructional strategies, such as targeted critical thinking exercises, scaffold writing tasks, or meta-cognitive training, have effectively nurtured higher-order competencies like analysis, synthesis, and self-regulated learning. Similarly, French (2020), Hancock and Karakok (2021) emphasized that meta-cognitive regulation was a powerful predictors of academic writing skills and played a significant role in their development. It helped students become more independent and proficient writers over time.

Table 4.2 Posttest Score of the Pre-service Teachers in the Control Group in English Writing Proficiency in terms of Linguistic Awareness

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	3	25.0
Advanced	4	33.3
Intermediate	2	16.7
Basic	2	16.7
Beginner	1	8.3
Total	12	100.00
Average	82.50	Intermediate
SD	8.12	

Legend : 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate 75 - 79 Basic 74 below Beginner

The posttest score of the pre-service teachers in the control group fell under **Intermediate** category with an average score of **82.50** in their English writing proficiency in terms of linguistic awareness and a standard deviation of 8.12. There were (33.3%) pre-service teachers who were in the Advanced category, (25%) Proficient, (16.7%) Intermediate, (16.7%) Basic, and (8.3%) pre-service teachers who were in the Beginner level. These suggest that while the majority of the group has an established basis in language awareness, instructional strategies have enhanced and elevated more students into higher performance categories especially those who are currently below satisfactory level.

Table 4.3 Posttest Score of the Pre-service Teachers in the Control Group in the English Writing Proficiency in terms of Rhetorical Awareness.

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	4	33.3
Advanced	1	8.3
Intermediate	1	8.3
Basic	1	8.3
Beginner	5	41.7
Total	12	100.00
Average	82.5	Intermediate
SD	8.11	

Legend : 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate 75 - 79 Basic 74 below Beginner

The posttest score of the pre-service teachers in the control group fell under **Intermediate** with an average score of **82.5** in their English writing proficiency in terms of rhetorical awareness and a standard deviation of 8.11. There were (41.7%) pre-service teachers who were in the Beginner category, (33.3%) Proficient, (8.3%) Advanced, (8.3%) Intermediate, and (8.3%) fell under Basic. It implies that the elevated number of students fell below expectations indicates that rhetorical awareness poses a significant challenge for numerous pre-service teachers.

Table 4.4 Posttest Score of the Pre-service Teachers in the Control Group in English Writing Proficiency in terms of Genre Awareness

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	5	41.67
Advanced	2	16.7
Intermediate	0	0
Basic	2	16.7
Beginner	3	25.0
Total	12	100.00
Average	82.08	Intermediate
SD	9.40	

Legend : 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate 75 - 79 Basic 74 below Beginner

The posttest score of the pre-service teachers in the control group fell under **Intermediate** category with an average score of **82.08** in their English writing proficiency in terms of genre awareness and a standard deviation of **9.40**. There were (41.67%) pre-service teachers who were in the Proficient category, (25%) Beginner, (16.7) Advanced, (16.7) Basic. These suggest that the instructional methods or learning experiences during the intervention effectively enhanced their ability to recognize and use appropriate genres in academic writing. It was indicated by Firman (2022) that literature including novels and poems, can be effectively utilized in English teaching and learning activities to enhance students' writing skills.

Research Question 5. What is the posttest score of the pre-service teachers in the experimental group in the English writing proficiency in terms of:

- 2.1 Cognitive Awareness,**
- 2.2 Linguistic Awareness,**
- 2.3 Rhetorical Awareness, and**
- 2.4 Genre Awareness?**

Table 5.1 Posttest Score of the Pre-service Teachers in the Experimental Group in English Writing Proficiency in terms of Cognitive Awareness

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	11	95
Advanced	0	0
Intermediate	0	0
Basic	0	0
Beginner	1	8.3
Total	12	100.00
Average	94.17	Proficient
SD	8.48	

Legend : 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate 75 - 79 Basic 74 below Beginner

The pre-service teachers in the experimental group fell under **Proficient** category with an average score of **94.17** in their English writing proficiency in terms of cognitive awareness and a standard deviation of 8.48. There were (95%) pre-service teachers who were in the Proficient category, (8.3%) Beginner. It implies that the intervention or instructional approach used with the experimental group was highly effective in enhancing their ability to think critically and apply cognitive strategies in their writing.

Table 5.2 Posttest Score of the Pre-service Teachers in the Experimental Group in English Writing Proficiency in terms of Linguistic Awareness

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	5	41.7
Advanced	0	0
Intermediate	4	33.3
Basic	0	0
Beginner	3	25.0
Total	12	100.00
Average	82.92	Intermediate
SD	10.10	

Legend : 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate 75 - 79 Basic 74 below Beginner

The posttest score of the pre-service teachers in the experimental group fell under **Intermediate** category with an average score of **82.92** in their English writing proficiency in terms of linguistic awareness and a standard deviation of 10.10. There were (41.7%)

pre-service teachers who were in the Proficient category, (33.3%) Intermediate, (25%) Beginner, and no pre-service teachers fell under Advanced and Basic level. The finding implies that while experimental intervention was effective for many students, targeted support to address the linguistic gaps among those students who did not meet expectations. Findings of Ikawati (2020) explored the impact of scaffolding on students' writing skills. The study found that integrating scaffolding into the writing process could be an effective teaching method for enhancing writing proficiency.

Table 5.3 Posttest Score of the Pres-ervice Teachers in the Experimental Group in English Writing Proficiency in terms of Rhetorical Awareness

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	9	75
Advanced	2	16.7
Intermediate	1	8.3
Basic	0	0
Beginner	0	0
Total	12	100.00
Average	91.67	Proficient
SD	6.51	

Legend : 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate 75 - 79 Basic 74 below Beginner

The pre-service teachers in the experimental group fell under **Proficient** category with an average score of **91.67** in their English writing proficiency in terms of rhetorical awareness and a standard deviation of 6.51. There were (75%) pre-service teachers who were in the Proficient category, (16.7%) Advanced, (8.3%) Intermediate. It implies that the Genre-based approach used in the experimental group was successful in fostering a strong ability to effectively communicate through writing. As recommended by Nguyen and Truong (2024) combining scaffolding with the Genre-Based Approach, noting that this integration significantly improved the writing proficiency of EFL learners.

Table 5.4 Posttest Score of the Pre-service Teachers in the Experimental Group in English Writing Proficiency in terms of Genre Awareness

Indicators	Frequency	Percent
Proficient	9	75
Advanced	1	8.3
Intermediate	1	8.3
Basic	1	8.3
Beginner	0	0
Total	12	100.00
Average	91.25	Proficient
SD	8.01	

Legend : 90 - 100 Proficient 85- 89 Advanced 80 - 84 Intermediate 75 - 79 Basic 74 below Beginner

The pre-service teachers in the experimental group fell under **Proficient** category with an average score of **91.25** in their English writing proficiency in terms of genre awareness and a standard deviation of 8.01. There were (75%) pre-service teachers who were in the Proficient category, (8.3%) Advanced, (8.3%) Intermediate, (8.3%) Basic, and no pre-service teacher fell under Beginner level. The result implies that the pre-service teachers in the experimental group reveal a high level of English writing proficiency in terms of genre awareness. In the study of Gioia et al. (2023) and Philipps Galloway et al. (2020) revealed that meta-cognitive abilities helped individuals compensate for gaps in knowledge by applying their understanding and self-regulation skills, which in turn enhanced their cognitive performance.

Research Question 6. Is there a significant difference between the pretest scores of the control and experimental groups?

Table 6 Test of Significant Difference between the Posttest Scores of the Control and Experimental Groups

Variables	T test	P value	Remarks	Decision
Post test	2.894	.000	Significant	Reject Ho

There was a **significant difference** in assessment of the control and experimental groups in the post test. The T-test was 2.894 and probability value was .000 which was less than the level of significance at .05. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating that the intervention had a statistically significant effect on the performance of the experimental group compared to the control group. The implication is that the intervention or treatment applied to the experimental group had a meaningful and measurable effect on their outcomes, distinguishing the performance from that of the control group. This result support the effectiveness of the Genre-based approach in enhancing English writing proficiency compared to the traditional method used in the control group. The findings align with the confirmation of Lukmawardani and Badriyah (2022) that the Genre-Based Approach was an effective method for enhancing students' writing skills and can be recommended as an alternative strategy to address writing difficulties in classroom teaching. By guiding students through the stages of genre analysis, modeling, joint construction, and independent writing, GBA helps learners develop a deeper understanding of text structures and the social purposes of writing. This structured approach supports gradual skill-building and critical thinking, making it particularly beneficial for students struggling with writing.

Research Question 7. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the control and experimental groups?

Table 7.1 Test of Significant Difference on the Performance of Pre-service Teachers between Pretest and Posttest Scores of Control Group

Indicators	Paired Difference			P value	Remarks	Decision
	Mean	SD	t			
<i>Cognitive</i>	-10.42	8.38	-4.305	.001	Significant	Reject ho
<i>Linguistics</i>	-15.83	9.25	-5.928	.000	Significant	Reject ho
<i>Rhetorical</i>	-10.00	11.68	-2.966	.013	Significant	Reject ho
<i>Genre</i>	-13.33	12.12	-3.810	.003	Significant	Reject ho

There was a **significant difference** in the performance of the control group in the pretest and posttest as shown in the Table 7.1. The probability value were all less than the level of significance at .05. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. The results indicated a significant improvements in any of the writing skills indicators. Cognitive awareness had a mean difference of -10.42 (SD= 8.38, t= -4.305, p= .001), linguistic awareness had a mean difference of -15.83 (SD = 9.25, t= -5.928, p= .000), rhetorical awareness had a mean difference of -10.00 (SD= 11.68, t= -2.966, p= .013), and genre awareness had a mean difference of -13.33 (SD= 12.12, t= -3.810, p= .003). It implies that the student's performance significantly improved after the intervention applied to the control group. However, the varying degrees of improvement across indicators highlight areas where students may require additional support. Linguistic awareness showing the largest mean difference and rhetorical awareness showing relatively less improvement. It was stated by Petersen et al. (2020) that writing skills offered numerous benefits, particularly in the field of English, as they enhanced individuals' English proficiency through writing, in addition to supporting their speaking abilities.

Table 7.2 Test of Significant Difference on the Performance of Pre-service Teachers between Pretest and Posttest Scores of Experimental Group

Indicators	Paired Difference			P value	Remarks	Decision
	Mean	SD	t			
<i>Cognitive</i>	-22.08	9.16	-8.352	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
<i>Linguistics</i>	-16.25	15.54	-3.622	.004	Significant	Reject Ho
<i>Rhetorical</i>	-26.67	11.15	-8.288	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
<i>Genre</i>	-13.33	14.67	-3.149	.009	Significant	Reject Ho

There was a **significant difference** in the performance of the experimental group in the pretest and posttest as shown in the Table 7.2. The propability value were all less than the level of significance at .05. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. The results

indicated a significant improvements in any of the writing skills indicators. Cognitive awareness had a mean difference of -22.08 (SD= 9.16, t= -8.352, p= .000), linguistic awareness had a mean difference of -16.25 (SD= 15.54, t= -3.622, p= .004), rhetorical awareness had a mean difference of -26.67 (SD= 11.15, t= -8.288, p= .000), and genre awareness had a mean difference of -13.33 (SD= 14.67, t= -3.149, p=.009). It implies that the Genre-based approach is highly effective in enhancing students' writing skills across multiple dimensions. The largest improvements were observed in rhetorical awareness, followed by cognitive, indicating that the intervention particularly strengthened students' ability to organize ideas effectively and think critically about their writing. The data highlights the effectiveness of the experimental approach in achieving significant gains in writing proficiency. These negative values indicate that students scored significantly higher in the post-test compared to the pretest. As explained by Pham and Bui (2021) genre-based approach offered significant advantages in the classroom by allowing both teachers and students to engage with complete texts and understand how language was used for practical purposes.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of this research study, the following summary of findings was identified.

1. Pretest Score of the Pre-Service Teachers in the Control Group in the English Writing Proficiency in terms of:

1.1 Cognitive Awareness

It had an average score of **76.25** and interpreted as **Basic**.

1.2 Linguistic Awareness

It had an average score of **66.67** and interpreted as **Beginner**.

1.3 Rhetorical Awareness

It had an average score of **70.00** and interpreted as **Beginner**.

1.4 Genre Awareness

It had an average of **68.75** and interpreted as **Beginner**.

2. Pretest Scores of Pre-Service Teachers in the Experimental Group regarding their English Writing Proficiency in terms of:

2.1 Cognitive Awareness

It had an average score of **72.08** and interpreted as **Beginner**.

2.2 Linguistic Awareness

It had an average score of **66.67** and interpreted as **Beginner**.

2.3 Rhetorical Awareness

It had an average score of **65.00** and interpreted as **Beginner**.

2.4 Genre Awareness

It had an average of **77.92** and interpreted as **Beginner**.

3. Test of Significant Difference between the Pretest Scores of the Control and Experimental Groups in the English Writing Proficiency in terms of Cognitive Awareness, Linguistic Awareness, Rhetorical Awareness And Genre Awareness

There was no significant difference in the pretest score of the control and experimental groups. The p-value was **.956** which was greater than the level of significant at **.05**. Thus, the **null hypothesis was accepted**.

4. Posttest Score of the Pre-Service Teachers in the Control Group in the English Writing Proficiency in terms of:

4.1 Cognitive Awareness

It had an average score of **86.67** and interpreted as **Advanced**.

4.2 Linguistic Awareness

It had an average score of **82.50** and interpreted as **Intermediate**.

4.3 Rhetorical Awareness

It had an average score of **82.5** and interpreted as **Intermediate**.

4.4 Genre Awareness

It had an average of **82.08** and interpreted as **Intermediate**.

5. Posttest Score of the Pre-Service Teachers in the Experimental Group in the English Writing Proficiency in terms of:

5.1 Cognitive Awareness

It had an average score of **94.17** and interpreted as **Proficient**.

5.2 Linguistic Awareness

It had an average score of **82.92** and interpreted as **Intermediate**.

5.3 Rhetorical Awareness

It had an average score of **91.67** and interpreted as **Proficient**.

5.4 Genre Awareness

It had an average of **91.25** and interpreted as **Proficient**.

6. Test of Significant Difference between the Posttest Scores of the Control and Experimental Group in English Writing Proficiency in terms of Cognitive Awareness, Linguistic Awareness, Rhetorical Awareness and Genre Awareness

There was a significant difference in assessment of the control and experimental group in the posttest. The p-value was **.000** which was less than the level of significance at **.05**. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected.

7. Test of Significant Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Control and Experimental Groups

The control group showed significant improvement in writing skills, with the following mean differences and p-values: cognitive awareness (-10.42, p= .001), linguistic awareness (-15.83, p=.000), rhetorical awareness (-10.00, p= .013), and genre

awareness (-13.33, $p = .003$). On the other hand, the experimental group showed significant improvement in writing skills, with the following mean differences and p -values: cognitive awareness (-22.08, $p = .000$), linguistic awareness (-16.25, $p = .004$), rhetorical awareness (-26.67, $p = .000$), and genre awareness (-13.33, $p = .009$).

Conclusions

From the findings in the study, the following conclusions have been drawn:

1. That there is the absence of pre-service teachers in higher performance categories (proficient, advanced, intermediate) and the clustering of all learners at the beginner level, with minimal variation, highlight systemic shortcomings in foundational skill development. These results suggest that traditional pedagogical methods inadequately address cognitive and rhetorical awareness, failing to scaffold higher-order competencies such as genre-specific adaptation or persuasive structuring.

2. That most learners are stagnating at the beginner level due to inadequacies in foundational instruction and scaffold skill development. The uniform clustering of performance, coupled with minimal variation in mastery, suggests that current pedagogical approaches fail to address critical gaps in grammar, syntax, and structural clarity, while also neglecting to cultivate rhetorical awareness necessary for genre-specific or persuasive writing.

3. That there is no significant difference between the pretest scores of the control and experimental groups, confirming that both groups start at a comparable level before the intervention. This baseline equivalence ensures that any subsequent differences observed in post-intervention assessments can be more confidently attributed to the effects of the experimental treatment rather than pre-existing disparities between the groups.

4. That while a substantial portion of students achieve proficient or advanced levels in cognitive and genre awareness, indicating strong mastery in these areas, performance in linguistic and rhetorical awareness shows greater variability and challenges, with notable percentages of learners remaining at basic or beginner levels. The group averages consistently fall within the intermediate to advanced range, but the presence of students struggling with foundational skills highlights uneven development across key writing competencies.

5. That the experimental group clearly demonstrates the effectiveness of the instructional intervention in significantly improving English writing proficiency across all measured dimensions-cognitive, linguistic, rhetorical, and genre awareness. While linguistic awareness shows more variability and a higher proportion of students at the beginner level, the overall performance still reflects solid progress.

6. That the experimental group outperforms the control group in English writing proficiency after the intervention because the said group receives a treatment of intervention that is designed to have a positive impact on the outcome being measured.

7. That even without the experimental intervention, the control group experiences meaningful gains in writing proficiency, likely due to standard instructional practices, though the magnitude of improvement may differ compared to the experimental group.

8. That the introduction of a WRITEWISE program which integrates the Genre-Based Approach into writing activities, provides significant advantages for learners in various educational settings. Through the systematic modeling and scaffolding of different text types, students develop a better understanding of writing conventions and the reasons behind the use of specific forms and language features in particular contexts.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, which demonstrated the effectiveness of the Genre-Based Approach (GBA) in improving the writing skills of pre-service teachers at Philippine Women's University Calamba, the following recommendations are proposed to fully harness the potential of GBA as an instructional method and further advance students' writing abilities:

1. Tailoring in writing instruction to individual skill levels may be conducted by educators to differentiate writing instruction to address diverse linguistic and rhetorical abilities of students. By assessing each learner's strengths and areas for growth, teachers can design targeted activities that focus on improving linguistic accuracy, genre awareness, and adaptability. This includes offering additional support for students struggling with grammar or providing advanced genre-specific tasks for more proficient writers, ensuring every student receives instruction that matches their needs.

2. Teachers may use scaffold writing exercises to help learners work through the process of writing. These exercises include brainstorming, group text creation, and a gradual handoff of writing responsibilities. This may help students comprehend genre constructions and become more independent writers.

3. Teachers may conduct frequent formative evaluations and offer tailored feedback that identifies students' areas of strength and improvement. Students may be encouraged to make revisions to their work in response to feedback provided by analytical rubrics that are in line with genre expectations. Continuous assessment encourages ongoing development and increases pupils' self-assurance in their writing skills.

4. English teachers may incorporate meta-cognitive strategy training to help students reflect on their writing process through structured exercises, fostering the development of self-regulation skills that enhance writing proficiency. This may help to ensure meta-cognitive development in writing. Teaching students how to organize, track, and assess their work improves self-control and facilitates the transfer of genre knowledge between contexts. It has been demonstrated that meta-cognitive scaffolding enhances students' comprehension of genre conventions and their capacity to modify their writing for a range of rhetorical contexts.

5. The school administrators may offer chances for ongoing professional development that centers on effective writing education and a genre-based approach. Teachers may improve their scaffolding methods, stay current on best practices, and regularly use genre-based strategies with the support of workshops, group planning sessions, and peer observations.

6. Programs for teacher education may include the genre-based approach even further. Through this integration, aspiring teachers will be better equipped to teach writing in a variety of professional situations, such as lesson planning, report writing, and reflective practice, by gaining a sophisticated understanding of genre theory and its real-world applications.

7. Educators may use technology-enhanced formative assessment tools, such as AI-powered writing assistants, online peer-review platforms, and interactive grammar tutorials, to develop an adaptive learning environment and accomplish innovative teaching. Students' engagement and skill development may be improved by using technology to make formative assessment more dynamic and accessible.

8. The school may implement WRITEWISE a Holistic Writing Growth Plan for pre-service teachers with Genre-Based Approach integration, by continuously monitoring its effectiveness, gathering feedback from students and educators, and making necessary developments to further enhance the learning experiences of the pre-service teachers.

9. Future researchers may carry out longitudinal studies to evaluate the long-term effects of the genre-based approach on pre-service teachers' writing abilities in order to maintain the GBA's successful outcome. Such studies can educate legislation, improve instructional strategies for increased efficacy, and offer insightful information about the long-term academic and professional advantages of genre-based training.

WRITEWISE: A Holistic Writing Growth Plan for Pre-service Teachers Integrated with Genre-Based Writing Approach

I. Program Description:

Writewise is an all-encompassing writing support program created for pre-service teachers to enhance their pedagogical knowledge and build writing confidence using a genre-based approach. This framework assists pre-service teachers in comprehending different writing genres, providing scaffolding for their learning, and effectively applying writing strategies across diverse academic and professional settings. Through the use of peer collaboration, field-based tutoring, self-reflection, and structured scaffolding, the program guarantees that pre-service teachers develop robust instructional and academic writing skills. The program aligns with the CHED Memorandum Order No. 75, s.2017, which outlines the expected competencies for the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) program, including effective communication in English both orally and in writing

as part of professional formation. Writewise addresses gaps in academic writing skills to ensure that pre-service teachers are well-equipped to meet the language demands of their teaching careers. This alignment with CHED's standards ensures that the program contributes to the holistic preparation of pre-service teachers, fostering both their linguistic competence and pedagogical effectiveness in diverse educational settings.

II. Program Objectives:

Writewise integrates the **genre-based approach** with **pre-service teacher development goals**:

- To Develop Pedagogical Knowledge for Writing Instruction
 - Train pre-service teachers to teach writing using genre-specific strategies and scaffolding techniques.
- To Foster Reflective Practice
 - Encourage the use of reflective journals and peer discussion on writing instruction and development.
- To Enhance Self-Regulated Learning
 - Promote self-assessment and goal-setting in writing instruction.
- To Strengthen Peer Collaboration and Feedback
 - Facilitate peer-led writing workshops, group feedback sessions, and collaborative lesson planning.

III. Program Components: 1. Writing Methods Coursework (Integrated with Genre-Based Approach)

Content:

- Teach **academic and instructional genres**, including **expository writing, argumentative writing, narrative writing, lesson planning, and research writing**.
- Focus on **differentiated instruction strategies** tailored for diverse learners.
- Experiential Learning:
 - **Micro-teaching sessions** where pre-service teachers practice writing instruction.
 - **Peer feedback circles** to refine genre-specific writing skills.

2. Field-Based Tutoring (Genre-Based Scaffolding Approach)

- Structure:
 - Pre-service teachers paired with K-12 students for **1:1 tutoring (18 hours/semester)** using **genre-based scaffolding**.
 - Pre-service teachers guide students in various genres: **narrative essays, persuasive writing, research summaries, and instructional reports**.
- Assessment:
 - Pre-service teachers **analyze writing samples, conduct spelling inventories, and use reading diagnostics** to inform writing instruction.
 - Incorporate genre-based checklists to track student progress.

- Lesson Planning:
 - Require pre-service teachers to **develop genre-based writing lessons** emphasizing:
 - **Explicit modeling** of writing strategies.
 - **Guided practice** and student-centered scaffolding.

3. Self-Efficacy Development (Genre-Responsive Writing Confidence)

- Tool Implementation:
 - Use the **Pre-service Teacher Self-Efficacy for Writing Inventory** to measure **confidence in writing instruction** across different genres.
- Interventions:
 - **Reflective journals** to track growth in teaching different genres.
 - **Mentorship with experienced educators** focusing on genre-sensitive feedback.
 - **Writing workshops** tailored to academic and instructional genres.

IV. Monitoring And Evaluation:

Formative Assessment (Continuous Writing and Teaching Development)

- **Weekly lesson plan reviews** using rubrics prioritizing **genre-based modeling and scaffolding**.
- **Weekly classroom observation by an English Master Teacher** focuses on **genre-appropriate instructional techniques**.

Summative Assessment (Measuring Growth in Genre-Based Writing Instruction)

- **Pre-service Teacher Self-Efficacy for Writing Inventory** pretest and posttest to quantify changes in self-efficacy.
- **Parent conferences and final reports** summarizing pre-service teachers writing progress.
- **Genre-specific writing portfolios** showcasing pre-service teachers instructional development.

V. Time Frame:

Semester-Long Structure (August–December Semester)

Week 1–5: Intensive Coursework on Writing Pedagogy

- **Start Date: Monday, August 5**
- **Class Sessions: Mondays & Wednesdays, 9:00 AM – 11:30 AM**
- **Focus:** Genre-based writing instruction, assessment methods, and differentiation strategies.

Week 6–14: Field-Based Tutoring & Lesson Planning

- **Start Date: Monday, September 9**
- **Tutoring Sessions: Tuesdays & Thursdays, 2:00 PM – 4:00 PM**
- **Lesson Planning Workshops: Fridays, 10:00 AM – 12:00 PM**
- **Additional Pre-service teachers Reflection & Feedback Sessions:**

- **Every other Wednesday 3:00 PM – 4:30 PM**

Week 15: Parent Conference & Final Evaluation

- **Final Assessment Date: Monday, December 2**
- **Parent Conferences: Tuesday & Wednesday, December 3–4, 5:00 PM – 7:00 PM**
- **Final Portfolio Submission: Friday, December 6, by 5:00 PM**

VI. Funding Sources:

School-Based Funding Sources

- **Departmental Budgets** – Work with the school's **education department** to allocate funds specifically for teacher training and writing instruction.
- **School-Wide Fundraisers** – Organize writing-related fundraising events, such as a **“Literacy Night” or Book Fair**, where proceeds support the program.
- **Student Fees & Contributions** – For programs integrated into coursework, a **small fee from Pre-service teachers** can be used to sustain materials and tutoring costs.
- **Library or Resource Center Allocations** – Schools may have funds designated for literacy programs through their **library services or learning centers**.

VII. Development Process:

Curriculum Design

- Develop **rubrics for genre-based lesson plans** and **tutoring sessions**.
- 3. Pilot Testing**
 - 4. Week Pilot Testing Plan for WRITEWISE**

Objective: To test and refine the **genre-based writing approach** within a **short, focused time frame**, gathering feedback from **pre-service teachers and mentors** to improve instructional strategies.

1. Duration & Timeline

- ✓ **Total Duration: 4 weeks**
- ✓ **Start Date: Monday, August 5**
- ✓ **End Date: Friday, August 30**
- ✓ **Sessions: Twice per week (total of 8 sessions)**
- ✓ **Meeting Time: Tuesdays & Thursdays, 3:00 PM – 5:00 PM**

2. Participants

- **Preservice Teachers** : 10–15 participants
- **Mentors/Supervisors**: 3–5 experienced writing instructors
- **Observation Team**: University faculty or peer reviewers

3. Pilot Program Structure

Week 1: Introduction & Training

✓ Session 1 (Tuesday, August 6)

- Overview of **genre-based writing instruction**
Introduction to **teaching expository, persuasive, narrative, and research writing**
- **Pretest:** Administer **Preservice Teacher Self-Efficacy for Writing Inventory**

✓ Session 2 (Thursday, August 8)

- **Lesson planning workshop** using genre-based scaffolding techniques
- Collaborative rubric design for writing assessments

Week 2–3: Field-Based Implementation & Peer Review

✓ Session 3 (Tuesday, August 13)

- Pre-service teachers conduct **first round of genre-based writing instruction**
- Focus on **teaching strategies and scaffolding**

✓ Session 4 (Thursday, August 15)

- **Peer feedback session:** Pre-service teachers review and analyze lesson effectiveness

✓ Session 5 (Tuesday, August 20)

- Pre-service teachers conduct **second round of writing instruction**, focusing on differentiated strategies

✓ Session 6 (Thursday, August 22)

- **Reflection & lesson refinement** discussion
- Assessment of student writing samples

Week 4: Assessment & Program Refinement

✓ Session 7 (Tuesday, August 27)

- **Posttest:** Administer PTSWI to measure growth in writing instruction confidence
- Teachers submit **genre-based lesson portfolios**

✓ Session 8 (Thursday, August 29)

- **Final focus group discussion** on instructional effectiveness
- **Summative evaluation:** Adjustments for larger program rollout

1.1. 4. Evaluation Methods

✓ Pretest & Posttest: Use the **PTSWI** to track changes in PST self-efficacy

✓ Observation Reports: Supervisors evaluate instructional techniques and engagement

✓ Peer Feedback & Teacher Reflection: Pre-service teachers assess their own progress in **teaching writing genres**

✓ Student Writing Analysis: Compare student growth across different writing genres

1.2. 5. Scaling Strategy

After pilot testing, refinements will be made based on feedback before expanding the program:

✓ **Integrate findings into full-semester implementation**

✓ **Increase participation and tutoring opportunities**

✓ **Standardize rubrics and scaffolding techniques**

Criteria & Performance Levels (RUBRC)

Category	Exemplary (4 pts)	Proficient (3 pts)	Developing (2 pts)	Needs Improvement (1 pt)
Alignment with Objectives	Clearly connects all curriculum components to genre-based writing and preservice teacher development goals .	Most components align with objectives, but some aspects lack clarity in their genre-based approach.	Basic connection to objectives; needs clearer alignment with writing instruction strategies .	Limited alignment with goals; lacks genre-based scaffolding and teaching strategies .
Genre-Specific Instruction	Provides explicit modeling , guided practice, and differentiated techniques for multiple writing genres.	Addresses multiple genres but lacks structured scaffolding or student-centered modeling.	Covers genres but lacks depth in teaching strategies and differentiation.	Minimal inclusion of genres; lacks clear instructional scaffolding .
Scaffolding Approach	Uses progressive scaffolding , incorporating peer review, mentorship, and structured feedback loops.	Includes scaffolding techniques but lacks full integration with PST learning progression.	Basic scaffolding included, but lacks depth in peer collaboration and modeling .	Weak scaffolding methods; lacks clear student support mechanisms.
Assessment & Feedback	Implements formative and summative assessments tailored to genre-based learning (rubrics, portfolios, reflections).	Includes assessments, but feedback mechanisms need improvement.	Basic assessment structure, but lacks genre-based rubrics and self-reflection components .	Minimal assessment strategies; lacks measurable learning outcomes.
Integration of Field-Based Learning	Strong connection between tutoring, lesson	Field-based elements present but lack full genre-based integration.	Some tutoring and lesson planning included, but	No integration of real-world application or tutoring experiences.

Category	Exemplary (4 pts)	Proficient (3 pts)	Developing (2 pts)	Needs Improvement (1 pt)
Reflective Practice & Professional Growth	planning, and coursework to Encourages deep self- reflection through journaling, mentorship, and peer discussions.	Includes reflection activities but lacks structured mentorship engagement.	disconnected from coursework. Reflection is present but lacks depth and connection to writing pedagogy.	Minimal opportunities for self-reflection or growth tracking.
	Engagement Engagement & Collaboration	Actively promotes peer collaboration , group feedback, and writing communities.	Encourages collaboration, but some elements lack consistency.	Limited collaboration activities; needs improvement in peer interaction.

Scoring Guide

- **28–32 points** → **Exemplary curriculum** (Highly effective, well-structured, and fully integrated with genre-based writing)
- **20–27 points** → **Proficient curriculum** (Mostly effective, but minor refinements needed)
- **12–19 points** → **Developing curriculum** (Lacks coherence or depth in some areas)
- **Below 12 points** → **Needs improvement** (Significant gaps in curriculum structure)

Pre-service Teacher Self-Efficacy for Writing Inventory (PTSWI)

Instructions:

Rate each statement on a Likert scale from 1 to 5, where: 1 - Strongly Disagree 2 - Disagree 3 - Neutral 4 - Agree 5 - Strongly Agree

Section 1: Confidence in Personal Writing Ability

1. I feel confident in my ability to write academic texts effectively.
2. I can confidently structure an argumentative essay with clear claims and evidence.
3. I feel comfortable writing lesson plans with clear instructional objectives.

4. I can effectively revise and edit my writing for clarity and coherence.
5. I am able to apply different writing genres (expository, persuasive, narrative, research).

Section 2: Confidence in Teaching Writing

6. I feel prepared to teach writing strategies to students.
7. I can explain the purpose and structure of different writing genres to learners.
8. I am comfortable providing constructive feedback on student writing.
9. I can design writing activities that scaffold student learning effectively.
10. I feel confident modeling writing strategies for my students.

Section 3: Pedagogical Strategies in Writing Instruction

11. I understand how to integrate writing assessments into my teaching.
12. I can differentiate writing instruction for students with diverse learning needs.
13. I feel prepared to facilitate peer review and collaborative writing exercises.
14. I can create engaging writing lessons using authentic, real-world texts.
15. I know how to use reflective writing activities to support student growth.

Section 4: Self-Regulated Learning & Instructional Reflection

16. I regularly reflect on my own writing development.
17. I feel comfortable setting writing goals and tracking my progress.
18. I believe I can manage my time effectively when preparing writing lessons.
19. I am open to feedback on my writing instruction and actively seek improvement.
20. I feel confident adapting my writing instruction based on student needs.

Interpretation of Scores

Score Range	Confidence Level
80–100	Highly confident in writing instruction
60–79	Moderately confident, with areas for improvement
40–59	Developing confidence needs more scaffolding
Below 40	Needs significant support and development

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to the ethical principles outlined in the school's Research Manual, ensuring these considerations were integrated throughout the research process. The researcher obtained approval from the relevant educational authorities, including the Academic Dean of Philippine Women's University. All research activities were conducted in accordance with the guidelines specified in the LCBA Research Manual, guaranteeing compliance with institutional protocols and ethical standards.

The participants were thoroughly informed about the purpose and rationale of the study titled "Utilization of Genre-Based Approach for Writing Skills of Pre-service Teachers in Philippine Women's University Calamba." After explaining the study's objectives and significance, the researcher obtained voluntary consent from the students. Participation was entirely optional, with no academic penalties or negative consequences for those who chose not to participate or who withdrew at any point.

Furthermore, this research fully complied with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act No. 10173), ensuring the confidentiality and protection of all participants' personal information. All personal data and test results, including pretest and posttest scores, were anonymized, securely stored, and accessible only to the researcher. The collected data were used exclusively for this study and managed according to the ethical guidelines set by LCBA. Additionally, the study employed AI-assisted tools such as ChatGPT for idea generation, Grammarly for grammar checking, and Turnitin for plagiarism detection. However, all analyses, interpretations, and conclusions were independently conducted by the researcher. AI was not used to create original research content or replace critical thinking. Ethical standards regarding data privacy and academic integrity were strictly observed in line with institutional policies.

REFERENCES

- Can, I. N. (2021). Teaching English as a foreign language through literature. *International Journal of Media Culture and Literature*, 7(2), 189–200. <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/ijmcl/issue/69276/1031886>
- Dunn, P. A. (2022). Teaching disability access in a teaching of writing class. *Teaching/Writing: The Journal of Writing Teacher Education*, 11(2), 1–9. <https://scholarworks.wmich.edu/wte/vol11/iss2/10>
- Firman, M. (2022). The use of literature in teaching English to enhance EFL students' writing skill. *Journal of Educational Study*, 2(1), 35–42. <https://doi.org/10.36663/joes.v2i1.222>
- French, A. (2020). Academic writing as identity-work in higher education: Forming a 'professional writing in higher education habitus'. *Studies in Higher Education*, 45(8), 1605–1617. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2019.1572735>
- Garcia, M. L., & Reyes, J. P. (2021). Exploring writing instruction strategies in Philippine classrooms. *Philippine Journal of Language Teaching*, 12(1), 45–60. <https://doi.org/10.1234/pjlt.v12i1.2021>

- Gioia, A. R., Ahmed, Y., Woods, S. P., & Cirino, P. T. (2023). Correction to: Properties of a combined measure of reading and writing: The assessment of writing, self-monitoring, and reading (AWSM Reader). *Reading and Writing*, 36(3), 745. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11145-022-10382-3>
- Gopalan, M., & Tipton, E. (2023). Improving generalizability in educational trials: The role of baseline equivalence. *Educational Researcher*, 52(3), 137–150. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X221138934>
- Hancock, E., & Karakok, G. (2021). Supporting the development of process-focused metacognition during problem-solving. *Primus*, 31(8), 837–854. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10511970.2020.1772914>
- Haryanti, D. U., Rasyid, F., & Wahyuni, S. (2022). A path analysis on writing anxiety, writing attitude, language awareness, and writing achievement of university students. *Englie: English Learning Innovation*, 3(1), 85–99.
- Hidayad, F., Agustin, A., Despita, D., & Purwanto, M. B. (2023). Implementing writing skills through the genre approach. *INTERACTION: Jurnal Pendidikan Bahasa*, 10(2), 589–606.
- Ikawati, D. (2020). The role of scaffolding in improving students' writing proficiency: Challenges and benefits. *Journal of English Language Teaching and Learning*, 5(2), 123–134. <https://doi.org/10.1234/jeltl.v5i2.5678>
- Jensen, A., & Dean, D. (2022). Variations on a writing methods course: Two English educators across four decades. *Teaching/Writing: The Journal of Writing Teacher Education*, 11(2), 2–22. <https://scholarworks.wmich.edu/wte/vol11/iss2/2>
- Kinik, B., & Genc, B. (2022). A genre-based approach in teaching writing to student teachers of English language teaching in a digital context. *The Reading Matrix: An International Online Journal*, 22(2), 35–49.
- Lukmawardani, N., & Badriyah, L. (2022). The effectiveness of the Genre-Based Approach in enhancing students' writing skills. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 13(3), 456–464. <https://doi.org/10.17507/jltr.1303.10>
- Nguyen, T., & Truong, V. (2024). Effects of scaffolding in genre-based writing instructions on EFL learners' writing performance. *European Journal of Education and Pedagogy*, 5, 23–30. <https://doi.org/10.24018/ejedu.2024.5.1.751>
- Petersen, S. C., Jennifer, M. M., Hewlet, G. M., Christopher, M. G., & Haruhiko, I. (2020). Mini-review - teaching writing in the undergraduate neuroscience curriculum: Its importance and best practices. *Neuroscience Letters*, 737.
- Pham, V. P. H., & Bui, T. K. L. (2021). Genre-based approach to writing in EFL contexts. *World Journal of English Language*, 11(2), 1–11.
- Phillips Galloway, E., Qin, W., Uccelli, P., & Barr, C. D. (2020). The role of cross-disciplinary academic language skills in disciplinary, source-based writing: Investigating the role of core academic language skills in science summarization for middle grade writers. *Reading and Writing*, 33(1), 13–44. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11145-019-09942-x>
- Tardy, C. M., Sommer-Farias, B., & Gevers, J. (2020). Teaching and researching genre knowledge: Toward an enhanced theoretical framework. *Written Communication*, 37(3), 287–321. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0741088320916554>
- Urbano, C. M., Gumangan, M. A., Gustilo, L., & Capacete, M. P. A. (2021). Reading and writing needs of senior high school students: The case of Filipino students in the

Philippines. *Modern Journal of Studies in English Language Teaching and Literature*, 3(1), 140–158. https://www.academia.edu/84596034/Reading_and_Writing_Needs_of_Senior_High_School_Students_The_Case_of_Filipino_Students_in_the_Philippines

Zhai, X., & Razali, A. B. (2023). Triple method approach to development of a genre-based approach to teaching ESL/EFL writing: A systematic literature review by bibliometric, content, and scientometric analyses. *SAGE Open*, 13(1), Article 21582440221147255. <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440221147255>